

USE OF FINANCIAL INSTRUMENTS IN ENSURING STABILITY OF INTERNATIONAL AGRICULTURAL TRADING

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the article is to study financial risk management tools in international agricultural trading in Ukraine in the context of a war economy (2022–2025). The study is based on a systematic approach to the analysis of financial instruments in combination with a functional cartography of agricultural trading risks. The methods of comparative analysis, structural and logical generalization, case method (using the example of the UNITY Facility and Solidarity Lanes programmes), and content analysis of official reports of international financial institutions were used. Three analytical objectives were sequentially fulfilled during the study, which allowed for a comprehensive assessment of the effectiveness of financial risk management tools in the field of international agricultural trading in Ukraine in the context of war (2022–2025). According to the first objective – building a “functional map” of instruments, it was proved that letters of credit, reserve guarantees, trade credit insurance, forward and futures contracts form the basic matrix of the financial stability of agricultural exports. Their use compensates for liquidity shortages, conversion restrictions, and increased insurance premiums, ensuring the continuity of foreign economic operations. According to the second objective, which covered channels of access to instruments through banks, export credit agencies and international financial organizations, it was established that the EBRD Trade Facilitation Programme plays a central role in maintaining payment discipline, while export credit agencies (in particular UKEF) support insurance coverage without reducing limits for Ukraine. The joint MIGA–EBRD and UNITY Facility programmes have proven the effectiveness of inter-institutional coordination between the state, the insurance market, and international banks. Finally, the third objective – a comparison of UNITY and Solidarity Lanes solutions – revealed the asymmetry, but also the complementarity of these mechanisms: the first reduces direct costs through insurance savings, the second – guarantees the continuity of physical flows even in case of escalation. Taken together, the results of the study confirm that the combination of marine insurance, trade finance, and currency hedging forms a multi-level system of countering risks, allowing Ukraine to maintain export stability, attract foreign capital, and increase the confidence of international counterparties in the Ukrainian market.

Keywords: bank guarantees, risk insurance, export credit agencies, documentary instruments, hedging, forward contracts, risk management, export recovery.

Problem statement

The war has sharply increased the volatility of logistics, prices, exchange rates, and counterparty risks, which has hit the working capital of agricultural exporters and the solvency of importers. In these conditions, financial instruments for risk management and liquidity provision play a key role. These include documentary transactions – letters of credit and bank guarantees, which minimize the risk of non-payment; trade risk insurance, guarantees from export credit agencies and international financial organizations, which compensate for losses in the event of breach of contracts; military and political risk insurance, which allows traders to cover losses from hostilities or changes in the regulatory environment; hedging instruments – futures and forward contracts (including currency), which enable fixing a price or rate and avoid losses from market fluctuations; as well as factoring and forfeiting, which ensure quick receipt of funds by selling receivables. Warehouse receipts and other forms of collateralized lending also play an important role, making it possible for agricultural producers and traders to obtain financing for confirmed product stocks, preserving working capital in times of crisis.

Therefore, the relevance of this study is determined by the need to find effective mechanisms for financial stabilization of the foreign economic activity of the agricultural sector of Ukraine in view of war risks

and limited access to capital. The loss of part of the export infrastructure, increasing cost of logistics, decreasing liquidity of the banking sector, and increasing cost of insurance coverage have led to the formation of a new configuration of financial flows in international agricultural trading. Accordingly, there is a need for an in-depth analysis of the effectiveness of existing financial instruments, their adaptation to war conditions and the involvement of international financial organizations to guarantee trade transactions. Through the prism of these challenges, it is appropriate to consider financial instruments not only as technical means of risk management, but as a strategic element of economic security and the restoration of Ukraine’s positions in the global agricultural market.

Analysis of recent research and publications

The analysis of studies confirms that the issue of financial instruments and risk management in the agricultural sector is quite actively explored in Ukraine. However, most of the studies cover the pre-war period and do not take into account the new configuration of market risks caused by the war. Solomatina T. V. [1] revealed insurance as a key tool for hedging the loss of financial potential of agricultural enterprises, emphasizing its stabilizing function, but without considering documentary and international guarantee schemes. Her conclusions are logically continued by Tsarenko D. G. [2], who considered financial instruments as a component of the risk management strategy of agricultural

business, having formed the conceptual principles of the system of financial protection of enterprises, but without adapting to war shocks.

From the perspective of market mechanisms, Motashko T. P. and Yakymets D. V. [3] proposed a typology of grain market risks and methods for minimizing them, focusing on internal management decisions. In this context, the research of M. and V. Dykha [4] developed the idea of using price risk hedging based on futures, options and over-the-counter contracts, which was the first step towards the practical use of derivatives in the agricultural sector. At the same time, Stelmakh D. V. [5] detailed the prospects for the development of hedging in the grain market, determining the conditions for the effectiveness of exchange transactions, but without integration with documentary financing or international guarantees.

Sokolyuk S., Smoliy L. and Zharun O. [6] studied the institutional dimension of the issue, determining the role of the state in minimizing agricultural risks and emphasizing the importance of state support policies and guarantee coverage. Their conclusions are consistent with the provisions of Kompanenko M. I. [7], who systematized the financial instruments of foreign economic activity of agribusiness and identified export credit agencies (ECAs) as a key link in restoring financial confidence.

For their part, Yatsenko O. [8] and Repina I. M. with Yatsenko O. M. [9] considered agricultural trading in a global dimension, studying the behavioural determinants of traders and their reaction to changes in the market, which gives grounds for analysing financial adaptation in view of wartime challenges. In the international context, Chikov I. et al. [10] emphasized the importance of innovative financing for the development of agro-food enterprises, substantiating the role of credit and guarantee programmes in stimulating exports.

Unresolved issues

Existing studies form a methodological framework for understanding the structure of risks and classic tools for their mitigation, but there is a lack of studies that would systematically analyse the interaction of banking, insurance, and interstate mechanisms in the wartime economy. Our research fills this gap by combining an assessment of documentary operations, international trade facilitation programmes (EBRD TFP,

MIGA–EBRD, UKEF), and the UNITY Marine War Risk insurance solution.

Aim of the article

The aim of the research is to study the role and effectiveness of financial instruments in ensuring the sustainability of international agricultural trading in Ukraine under martial law (2022–2025), in particular, assess their ability to minimize liquidity risks, currency fluctuations, logistical disruptions and counterparty defaults. Research objectives:

1. Create a “functional map” of financial risk management tools (letters of credit, guarantees, insurance, factoring, hedging, etc.) used in the military economy of Ukraine, and to determine their anti-crisis effectiveness in the agricultural trading sector.

2. Analyse the channels of access to financial instruments through banks, export credit agencies, and international financial organizations, reveal the mechanisms of guarantees, reinsurance and currency hedging that ensure the liquidity of trading operations.

3. Conduct a comparative analysis of the Ukrainian risk management model, in particular the UNITY Facility marine insurance programme and the Solidarity Lanes land corridor initiative, determine the optimal combination of financial and logistical tools to increase the resilience of supply chains and minimize systemic export risks.

Results

After the onset of the full-scale war, traditional financial models of agricultural exports underwent a profound transformation. Ukrainian traders found themselves in a situation where the usual supply channels, insurance methods, and sources of financing ceased to work or became excessively expensive. At the same time, it was the ability to quickly adapt to the new risk architecture that determined which of the market participants managed to maintain their positions in the global food chains. Therefore, there was a need to systematize and quantify those risks that directly affect the exporters’ financial stability. They differ in nature, but are interconnected, forming a single structure of threats for Ukrainian agricultural trading. Summarizing the results of the analytical review, four main risk nodes can be identified: logistical, counterparty, currency-price, and liquidity, which require specific neutralization tools. Their mutual correspondence is presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Mapping of agricultural export risks and relevant financial instruments for 2022–2025

Risk Area	Specification of war shock	Financial mitigation instruments	Implementation mechanisms and application examples
1	2	3	4
Maritime Logistics, Navigation	Blockade of ports, shelling, additional insurance premium for war risk (war premium)	War and political risk insurance (covering losses from hostilities, port blockades or sanctions), marine hull and carrier liability (Protection and Indemnity (P&I)) insurance, as well as special “corridor” schemes – state and international insurance programmes for transportation through agreed safe routes (for example, the grain corridor or the UNITY programme).	UNITY Facility is a joint initiative of Marsh, Lloyd’s, the Government of Ukraine, and the Export Credit Agency of Ukraine, aimed at reducing the cost of insurance for shipments to the war risk zone. Launched in November 2023 to insure grain exports through Black Sea ports, and expanded to all civilian cargoes (metal, containers, fertilizers, etc.) from March 2024. Thanks to this, insurance premiums for vessels calling at Ukrainian ports have decreased by 2–3 times, which has restored the competitiveness of maritime exports [11].
Counterparty risk	Payment disruptions, sanctions and jurisdictional restrictions	Letters of credit (LC) – a form of payment in which the bank guarantees payment to the exporter after the terms of the contract are fulfilled, which reduces the risk of non-payment; standby letters of credit (sBLC) – an additional bank guarantee that is activated only in the event of non-fulfilment of obligations by the buyer; trade credit insurance – protects the supplier against non-payment by a foreign partner or political restrictions; bank guarantees – ensure the fulfilment of contractual obligations.	EBRD Trade Facilitation Programme (TFP) is a programme of the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development that guarantees payments under letters of credit, standby letters of credit, and bank guarantees of Ukrainian banks, covering both commercial risks (non-payment by counterparties) and political risks (sanctions, restrictions, military events). Thanks to this, Ukrainian exporters have retained access to international markets even during the period of high turbulence in 2022–2025, and banks have the opportunity to open confirmed letters of credit with the involvement of foreign financial partners [12].
Currency risk (hryvnia - foreign currencies)	Managed hryvnia exchange rate, currency restrictions, exchange rate fluctuations	Forward and swap transactions – fix the exchange rate and protect against currency fluctuations; natural hedging – matching the currencies of income and expenses; letters of credit in the contract currency – ensure settlements without losses from exchange rate changes.	Since 2022, the National Bank of Ukraine (NBU) has maintained strict currency restrictions; in 2025, liberalization of the foreign exchange market began: forward contracts were allowed to be concluded to hedge imports and services, and exchange rate flexibility was expanded [13].
Price risk (grain, oil)	Sharp fluctuations in stock market quotes due to attacks, blockades or disruptions in logistics	Futures and options contracts (CBOT, Euronext) enable fixing the future price of grain or oilseeds; over-the-counter (OTC) derivatives – individual agreements between traders to hedge non-standard risks; formula pricing – calculation of the price by reference to a stock index or average quote for the period.	Ukrainian exporters fix the sales price as the sum of the exchange futures price and the local “basis” (the difference that takes into account logistics and product quality), and when exchanges are illiquid, they insure risks through individual over-the-counter (OTC) transactions with banks or partners.
Working capital, liquidity	Lengthening of the logistics cycle through EU Solidarity Lanes routes, increasing the need for turnover financing	Pre-export financing under contract or warehouse receipts, factoring, forfeiting, lending under the guarantees of export credit agencies (ECA-backed loans).	According to the European Commission, Ukraine has exported over 189 million tons of goods through Solidarity Lanes since May 2022 [14]. Regarding the EBRD: the news item “EBRD strikes risk-sharing deal for Ukraine trade finance” indicates that the EBRD has concluded agreements to develop risk-sharing mechanisms in Ukraine’s trade finance through the TFP programme [15].

Source: developed by the authors based on analysis [11-15]

The results summarized in Table 1 show that the system of financial protection of Ukrainian agricultural exports in 2022–2025 has been formed as a multi-level risk management structure, combining private, public, and international instruments. War shocks have shifted the emphasis from traditional bank financing to insurance and guarantee mechanisms (UNITY Facility, ECA, EBRD TFP), which ensure the continuity of contracts even in the high risk zone. Financial derivatives and forward contracts legalized and supported by the NBU began to play a key role in the field of exchange rate and price risks. They created conditions for the gradual return of flexibility to the foreign exchange market. The working capital of Ukrainian exporters is partially compensated through pre-export lending, factoring, and risk-sharing programmes, which have become an alternative to classic bank loans. So, financial instruments perform not only a compensatory, but also a stabilizing function, supporting the stability of Ukraine's international trade relations in wartime.

Upon determining the structure of risks and relevant instruments, it is necessary to analyse the mechanisms of access to them and the formation of the value of financial resources, which directly affect the competitiveness of Ukrainian exporters. That is why the next objective is to study the channels of access and pricing of financial instruments through banks, ECAs, and international financial organizations (IFOs) for 2022–2025.

Banking channels. Ukrainian banks play a key role in ensuring international settlements, acting as issuing banks for letters of credit, standby letters of credit, and bank guarantees of various types – LC/sBLC, bid bonds, performance bonds, advance-payment guarantees. At the same time, they attract trade credit lines to support customers – exporters and importers. The main problem of such operations is the high country risk and the limited willingness of foreign banks to confirm documents of Ukrainian issuers. That is why the EBRD TFP assumes guarantee obligations to international banks that act as confirming parties, covering both commercial and political risks of non-payment under letters of credit and guarantees opened by Ukrainian banks [12]. This allows access to confirmed letters of credit in major markets, reduces capital requirements and limits for Ukrainian banks, and reduces the discount when forfeiting, as part of the risk is transferred to the EBRD. By 2024, the TFP programme supported thousands of trade transactions with a total volume of billions of euros, which is directly confirmed by the EBRD's official description: “We provide guarantees to confirming banks, thereby covering the political and commercial risk of payment for transactions by issuing banks” [12].

ECAs. For supplies to Ukraine, a number of ECAs did not close the coverage after 2022, but on the contrary, maintained and expanded it. A telling example is UK Export Finance (UKEF): in the 2024-2025 financial year, the UK government officially confirmed the maintenance of the pre-war “country limit” for Ukraine of £3.5 billion, which allows insuring and guaranteeing contracts (infrastructure, equipment, logistics), while

indirectly reducing the cost of imported components (plant protection products, machinery) and financing for export contracts. By March 2025, the media noted that UKEF had actually chosen this limit within the limits of the provided capacity for Ukraine. Collectively, this supports suppliers' access to long-term and relatively cheaper resources under state guarantees, and for banks reduces capital requirements for country/counterparty risk [16].

International financial organizations. In the post-conflict environment, IFOs guarantee programmes play a significant role in supporting Ukraine's trade finance, in particular the MIGA–EBRD partnership, enshrined in the Memorandum of Understanding in February 2023 [17]. The programme provides insurance coverage against political risks (sanctions, hostilities, asset freezes) for operations financed by Ukrainian banks or international partners. Such coverage allows banks to reduce capital burdens and restore credit limits for trade operations related to the supply of food, energy, and medicines. MIGA emphasizes that these guarantees allow private financial institutions to continue operating even in high-risk countries, including Ukraine, ensuring the continuity of critical imports and exports.

Matine war risk. The launch of the UNITY Facility insurance solution (Marsh, Lloyd's, Government of Ukraine, State Export Credit Agency, state-owned banks) in November 2023 and expansion in March 2024 was a turning point for the restoration of maritime logistics. The initiative is aimed at covering war risks for vessels calling at Ukrainian Black Sea ports, in particular for the transportation of grain, metals, containerized and industrial cargo. Thanks to joint reinsurance through Lloyd's and support from the Ukrainian government, war-premiums for vessels decreased by 2–3 times, which made sea routes economically profitable. UNITY became not only an insurance but also a reputational signal of the restoration of trust in Ukrainian ports, stabilizing freight rates and exporters' netback.

NBU regulation and FX hedging: 2022–2025. The NBU's currency policy evolved from tight control to gradual liberalization during 2022–2025. After introducing strict currency restrictions in 2022 to stabilize the market and preserve reserves, in 2024 the regulator announced the second stage of currency liberalization, which provided for the relaxation of administrative control and the expansion of business access to hedging instruments [18]. A key step was the NBU Resolution No. 95 of August 5, 2025, which officially allowed the conclusion of forward contracts for the purchase and sale of currency, including transactions without the delivery of the underlying asset. This opened up the opportunity for Ukrainian companies to effectively hedge currency risks during import and export settlements [19]. Expert analytical reviews confirm that this reform significantly expanded the risk management tools of Ukrainian enterprises, bringing currency regulation closer to European practices [20].

Therefore, the analysis showed that the financial architecture of Ukraine's international agricultural trading gradually recovered in 2022–2025 thanks to the coordinated efforts of the banking sector, ECAs, IFOs,

and state initiatives to insure war risks. Banking channels supported by the EBRD TFP ensured the continuity of documentary settlements and the restoration of limits to Ukrainian banks in the face of war risk. Export credit agencies, primarily UKEF, maintained pre-war coverage limits (£3.5 billion), which allowed financing of critical imports of equipment and infrastructure, creating a multiplier effect for the export sector. IFOs, in particular the MIGA–EBRD partnership, introduced political risk guarantees, which allowed banks to reduce capital requirements and maintain liquidity for trade finance. At the same time, insurance solutions such as the UNITY Facility have restored maritime routes, while the NBU's currency liberalization has cre-

ated a basis for more predictable hedging of risks in external contracts. Together, these mechanisms have formed a synergistic resilience system where private and public financial instruments interact, minimizing the effects of war turbulence.

Given the developed multi-level support infrastructure, a logical step is to assess the effectiveness of its individual components, primarily in the field of transport and logistics solutions, which directly affect the financial risks of exports. Next, approaches to risk reduction in international agricultural trading will be compared using the example of two key mechanisms – marine insurance and land logistics, which differently affect the cost, liquidity and stability of Ukraine's export flows (Table 2).

Table 2

Comparison of risk reduction mechanisms in international agricultural trading in Ukraine (2022–2025)

Item No.	Criterion	UNITY Facility (maritime risks)	Solidarity Lanes (land/river routes)
1	The essence of the tool	War Risk Insurance Initiative for Shipping, a joint programme of Marsh, Lloyd's, the Government of Ukraine, the State ECA and state banks; covers risks for vessels calling at Ukrainian Black Sea ports.	EU logistics corridors, created in 2022 for the export of Ukrainian products via rail, road and river routes through the territory of EU countries.
2	Advantages	Direct savings on insurance premiums, restoration of access to the most efficient route (sea), increase in net sales revenue.	Geographical diversification of supplies, less dependence on maritime escalation, ensuring physical continuity of exports even during port blockades.
3	Disadvantages	High dependence on the military situation, limitations due to damage to port infrastructure.	Extended financial cycle and higher logistics costs due to transit complexity.
4	Key changes/events 2024–2025	In March 2024, coverage was expanded from “grain” to all non-military cargo (metal, containers, fertilizers), which reduced the average risk rate and stimulated sea transportation.	By September 2024, Solidarity Lanes ensured the transportation of about 154 million tons, and by March 2025 – 176 million tons of goods, supporting the liquidity of the agricultural market and price stability.
5	Economic effect	Reduction of insurance costs by 2–3 times, increase of exporters' margins, partial restoration of freight attractiveness of Ukrainian ports.	Maintaining the stability of export flows, maintaining foreign exchange earnings, supporting the transport integration of Ukraine with the EU.
6	Optimal usage strategy	Use UNITY to reduce insurance premium and return to sea routes at an acceptable level of risk.	Use as backup routes, securing financing under LC/sBLC, TFP, ECAs, as well as hedging currency and price risks during longer logistics.

Source: developed by the authors based on analysis [11-20]

Therefore, a comparative analysis shows that both mechanisms – UNITY Facility and Solidarity Lanes – play a strategically complementary role in ensuring the sustainability of Ukrainian agricultural trading, but their impact differs in the nature of risk and financial consequences. Marine insurance through UNITY creates a direct liquidity effect, as it reduces insurance premiums and instantly improves exporters' cash flows. At the same time, land logistics creates a temporary stability effect, providing a permanent, albeit more expensive, channel for exporting products even in the event of military escalation. UNITY is not only an insurance, but also a signalling initiative that has changed the perception of Ukrainian risk among international insurers

and creditors, helping to restore confidence in the port sector. Solidarity Lanes, in turn, have become an institutional guarantee of trade continuity, where the key resource is not a premium or guarantee, but time and geographical diversification, which reduce the systemic risk of a blockade. Together, these two channels create an asymmetric but complementary risk management model in which financial instruments (insurance, letters of credit, hedging) are integrated with the logistics infrastructure, ensuring not only physical delivery, but also the stability of foreign exchange earnings and exporters' margins.

Conclusions and propositions

The study showed that complex financial instruments that combine banking, insurance and interstate mechanisms play a key role in ensuring the stability of Ukraine's international agricultural trading in the war economy of 2022–2025. The “functional map” of instruments proved that effective risk management is possible only provided their combined use. The aforementioned EBRD TFP provides liquidity and reduces the risks of non-payment, UKEF and MIGA–EBRD create a system of guarantees and insurance of political risks, and the UNITY Facility restores the insurance availability of maritime transportation. In combination with Solidarity Lanes, they form a multi-level model of the sustainability of trade flows.

It was proved that financial instruments not only compensate for military restrictions, but also act as a catalyst for economic adaptation, i.e. through cheaper insurance premiums, reduced risk of defaults and expanded access to international financing. The obtained results have practical significance for further shaping of a system of trade guarantees, modernization of the insurance market, and integration of Ukrainian banks into global export financing chains. In the future, the effectiveness of agricultural trading will depend on the ability of the state, IFOs, and the banking sector to synchronize risk management policies, ensuring stable trade channels even under high uncertainty.

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